

A STUDY OF ACHIEVEMENT AND CONCEPT ACHIEVEMENT IN MATHEMATICS AT ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STAGE

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study was to study the achievement and concept achievement of sixth grade students in mathematics at elementary school stage. TTCATM comprising of 50 was administered to 1000 sixth-grade students. After the identification of achievement and prior to the identification of concept achievement, false positives and lack of knowledge were observed in between. In addition, the analysis of data showed that gender and location did not have significant effect on achievement and concept achievement of students.

Keywords: Achievement and Concept Achievement, Achievement, Concept Achievement, Mathematics, Elementary School Stage

Introduction

The National Curriculum Framework (NCF) developed by National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) in 2005, recommends a paradigm shift from rote memory to learning by understanding. Learning is simply the process of adjusting our mental models to accommodate new experiences. Meaningful learning is a generative process of representing and manipulating concrete things and mental representations, rather than storage and retrieval of information.

Constructivists thought learning process as an internal and active process, which develops within a learner. They included learner in the learning process. In constructivism, knowledge is created in the mind of the learner i.e. the student attempts to make sense of his/her world using previously acquired knowledge through everyday experiences or formal learning. In reality learning is process of construction and reconstruction of knowledge (Khader, 2005). Learning is an internal process and influenced by the learner's personality, prior knowledge and learning goals (Davidson, 1995).

In fact, learning is a process how the learner arrives at a particular answer. It is the process of building conceptual structures through reflection and abstraction (Von-Glasersfeld, 1995) and the foci are on the concept development and understanding (Fosnot, 1996). In the same way, the major

goal of Mathematics instruction in the elementary schools is the development of conceptual understanding. Throughout our instructional arrangements, we intend to organize examples and situations in such a way that the learner will be able to acquire the concepts (Pandey, 1983).

The structure of Mathematics can be compared to the framework of a building under construction. A framework of a building consists of a foundation, vertical pillars and horizontal beams. The foundation of the framework is comparable to the concepts, broad generalizations and principles of Mathematics, the vertical pillars to theories and horizontal beams to methods of Mathematics. If the base (foundation) will be strong, the building in turn will also be strong. Mathematics learning for most of the students involves the conceptual change.

Traditionally, classroom experiences emphasize rote learning. But Mathematics education is now increasingly finding a base on constructivist, cognitive and social learning theories which consider a human being as an active constructor of knowledge rather than as being passive recipient of environment stimuli. Learning is characterized by a process of interaction between the student's mind and the stimuli providing new information. Such a learning environment enables students to modify their existing cognitive structures and to experience a dynamic interaction between their preconceptions and the appropriate mathematical conceptions. According to Ausubel (1968), Piaget (1971) and Nurrenberg (2001) a learner organizes knowledge structures depending on his/her range of experiences through assimilation and accommodation. New knowledge is constructed by the learner through equilibrium between the above.

Prior knowledge forces a theoretical shift in viewing learning as 'conceptual change' (Strike and Posner, 1985; West and Pines, 1985). The learning cycle has been used to structure Mathematics instructions in order to help students move from concrete experience to formal abstract thinking about content. This constructivist approach is in turn based on Piaget's theory of intellectual development. According to this, development is structured by three teaching phases: Exploration, concept invention/introduction and application. Through this sequence, students' thinking is expected to progress from concrete thinking about mathematical concepts to being able to deal with these concepts on a formal abstract level. So engaging the students in a quest for knowledge to develop their rational power to think through this learning cycle and refine the everyday knowledge formed by observation of natural world was among the purposes of Mathematics education. This is called Conceptual Change Approach.

A large proportion of mathematical concepts require students to operate at the formal operational level of intellectual development. But a large number of students do not use formal operational thinking while dealing with such concepts and problems. They exhibit large differences in their ability to grasp and understand mathematical concepts. This mismatch between the levels of pupils thinking and the intellectual demand of the subject-matter is one of the major causes of learning difficulties in Mathematics.

Concept learning is regarded as the identification of the concept attributes, which can be generalized to newly encountered examples and discriminate examples from non-examples (Vaidya, 1997). Learning of a concept is a broader term, which includes most of the terms of conceptual learning. Learning a concept is a form of problem solving (Travers, 1977) because discovering the meaning of the concepts involves problem solving. While reading mathematical texts, students often try to rote learn facts, principles, formulas and rules instead of trying to understand them. They learn so that they can 'report back' information but not apply it. Teacher often mistakenly consider these achievements as concept achievement. But all the achievement may not be the concept achievement. After the identification of achievements and prior to the identification of concept achievement: false positives and lack of knowledge may emerge in between.

Many learners are impeded by the perceived difficulty of concepts presented to them and in the mode of presentation. Therefore, students' conceptual structures are studied in all curricular areas in the hope of remediating such impediments to learning.

Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the percentage of achievement and concept achievement of elementary school students on Three-Tier concept achievement test in Mathematics.
2. To study the dimensions of achievement and concept achievement of rural and urban elementary school students on Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics.
3. To study the dimensions of achievement and concept achievement of male and female elementary school students on Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between rural and urban elementary school students in Mathematics on Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics in terms of:
 - (i) Achievement
 - (ii) Concept Achievement
 - (iii) False Positives
 - (iv) Lack of Knowledge (Concept Achievement Wise)
2. There is no significant difference between male and female elementary school students in Mathematics on Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics in terms of:
 - (i) Achievement
 - (ii) Concept Achievement
 - (iii) False Positives
 - (iv) Lack of Knowledge (Concept Achievement Wise)

Methodology

Considering the nature of the problem under investigation descriptive survey method of research was used.

Tool

Standardized Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics (TTCATM) for sixth class comprised of 50 items having three tiers was used to study the dimensions of achievement and concept achievement of elementary school students.

Sampling

Multi-stage sampling was employed for the selection of sample for the study. 1000 sixth class students from 44 elementary, high and senior secondary schools of Punjab comprised the sample for present study, which includes equal number of male & female students and rural & urban students.

Analysis and Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive and inferential statistical techniques: percentage analysis, frequency distributions, central tendencies, standard deviation and t-test were used to analyze the data. The results of analysis of data are shown in the following tables (1-3) and figures:

Conclusions

1. A large proportion of students (71.90%) had correctly identified ray in a plane figure but 52.40% of them had correct reasoning with confidence. A small proportion of students (29.40%) had correctly selected that unlimited number of rays could be drawn through a point but with false reasoning and showing no confidence. Further, 40.20% of students had correctly identified ray in a complex figure.
2. A considerable proportion of students (49.40%) had correctly identified line in a complex figure but only 20.70% of them had correct reasoning with confidence. Small proportion of students (10%) had correctly identified line in a plane figure along with correct reasoning and confidence.
3. A considerable proportion of students (44.20%) had correctly identified line-segment in a plane figure but only few of them (8.20%) had correct reasoning with confidence. Small proportion of students (12%) had correctly identified line-segment in a complex figure with correct reasoning and confidence.

4. A large proportion of students (73%) had correctly identified angle but only 37.80% of them had correct reasoning with confidence. A considerable proportion of students (36.10%) had false positives about notation of angles. 11.30% of them had concept achievement wise lack of knowledge in identification of angle of measure 85° . A very small proportion of students (1.30%) had concept achievement wise lack of knowledge regarding identification of angle of

Table 1
Content Wise and Item Wise Comparison of Achievement, Concept Achievement, False Positives and Lack of Knowledge on TTCATM (Percentage Analysis)

Content	Item No.	Achievement	Concept Achievement	False Positives	Lack of Knowledge
Ray	1	71.9	52.4	16.8	2.7
	2	63.8	26.8	29.4	7.6
	3	40.2	30.6	4.5	5.1
Line	4	35	10.2	22.4	2.4
	5	49.4	20.7	25.6	3.1
Line -Segment	6	44.2	8.2	32	4
	7	42.9	12	26.4	4.5
Angle	8	73	37.8	31.2	4
	9	62.8	16.5	36.1	10.2
	10	55.5	21.9	27.4	6.2
	11	54.4	15.4	27.7	11.3
	12	46.2	13.7	28.7	3.8
	13	35.7	26.7	7.7	1.3
	14	39.3	20.2	8.4	10.7
	15	32.7	9.6	21.8	1.3
	16	31.5	9.8	19.5	2.2
	Pairs of Angles	17	70.1	15	51.4
18		57.5	5.7	49.1	2.7
19		69.4	24.3	37.1	8
20		45	15	29.1	0.9
21		42.6	8.7	23	10.9
22		65.2	48.6	5.4	11.2
23		73.6	14.9	50.3	8.4
24		13.1	9.4	2	1.7
25		42.6	18.6	20.4	3.6
26		27.7	10.1	10.7	6.9
27		41	13.1	26.7	1.2
Transversal and Pairs of Angles	28	71.1	29.3	34.2	7.6
	29	63.7	14.7	47	2
	30	65.9	17.4	37.8	10.7
Parallel Lines and Pairs of Angles made by Transversal	31	48.1	11.4	32.6	4.1
	32	79.9	11.1	47.9	20.9
	33	48.7	5.8	31.5	11.4
	34	18.5	11.9	2.4	4.2
Triangle	35	17.3	8.1	7.6	1.6
	36	57.1	26.6	25.9	4.6
	37	32.3	3.4	28	0.9
	38	45.1	27.5	6.9	10.7
	39	45.3	30.8	12.9	1.6
	40	40.9	5.5	34	1.4
	41	62.5	30.6	25	6.9
	42	45.2	21.1	22.1	2
	43	39.9	6.9	31.6	1.4
	44	42.5	22.2	16.6	3.7
	45	72.8	38.9	27.5	6.4
	46	59.9	14.4	45.1	0.4
	47	58.3	51.7	2.6	4
	48	24.4	18.9	2.1	3.4
	49	75.4	3.1	63.3	9
	50	66.3	11.2	54.4	0.7

Figure 1
Figure 2

Table 2
Comparison of Mean Differences in Performance of Elementary School Students on Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics in relation to Location

Dimensions	Location				
		N	Mean	S. D.	t-Value
Achievement	Urban	500	25.10	3.64	0.04
	Rural	500	25.11	3.65	
Concept Achievement	Urban	500	9.31	3.05	0.78
	Rural	500	9.46	3.02	
False Positives	Urban	500	13.19	3.02	0.62
	Rural	500	13.07	3.11	
Lack of Knowledge	Urban	500	2.56	1.6	0.77
	Rural	500	2.64	1.67	

Table 3
Comparison of Mean Differences in Performance of Elementary School Students on Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics in relation to Gender

Dimensions	Gender				
		N	Mean	S. D.	t-Value
Achievement	Male	500	25.09	3.53	0.13
	Female	500	25.12	3.76	
Concept Achievement	Male	500	9.36	3.02	0.26
	Female	500	9.41	3.04	
False Positives	Male	500	13.1	3.05	0.31
	Female	500	13.16	3.09	
Lack of Knowledge	Male	500	2.65	1.67	0.97
	Female	500	2.55	1.6	

measure 270° . Only some of the students (9.60%) had correctly identified reflexive angle with correct reasoning and confidence. However, 31.50% of students had correctly identified complete angle.

5. A large proportion of students (70.10%) had correctly defined the pair of adjacent angles, but most of them (51.40%) did not have correct reasoning. Nearly half of the students (48.60%) had correctly said that two right angles could be supplementary with correct reasoning and showing confidence. A small proportion of students (5.70%) had correctly identified vertically opposite angles with correct reasoning and confidence. A very little proportion of students (0.90%) did not correctly identify the relationship between linear pair of angles and supplementary angles with correct reasoning and confidence. 13.10% of students had correctly identified adjacent angles.
6. A large proportion of students (71.10%) had correctly identified the transversal but only some of them (29.30%) had correct reasoning and confidence. A considerable proportion of students (47%) had correctly identified exterior angles but with incorrect reasoning. Small

proportion of students (10.70%) had not shown confidence in identifying alternate interior angle though they had correct reasoning

7. A large proportion of students (79.90%) had correctly said that each pair of corresponding angles was equal, but 47.90% of them did not have correct reasoning and 20.90% of them had not shown confidence. Some students (11.90%) had correctly calculated the value of the angle with correct reasoning and confidence. 11.90% of students had correctly identified the relationship of parallel lines and interior angles with correct reasoning and confidence. 4.10% of students had correctly identified parallel lines with correct reasoning but had no confidence. Only some of the students (18.50%) had correctly identified the relationship of parallel lines and alternate interior angles with correct reasoning and confidence.
8. A very small proportion of students (2.10%) had correctly identified equilateral triangle but with incorrect reasoning. A significant proportion of students (51.70%) had correctly said that an isosceles triangle had two sides equal with correct reasoning and confidence. Small number of students (10.70%) had correctly identified the triangle part with correct reasoning but showed no confidence. 17.30% of students had correctly defined triangle. A few of them (0.40%) had not shown confidence in correctly identifying the obtuse angled triangle though they had correct reasoning. Only 3.10% of the students had correctly identified equilateral triangle with given measures of sides with correct reasoning and confidence.

Conclusions

On the basis of comparison of mean differences it was found that

1. There is no significant difference between rural and urban elementary school students in Mathematics on Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics in terms of achievement, concept achievement, false positives and lack of knowledge.
2. There is no significant difference between male and female elementary school students in Mathematics on Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics in terms of achievement, concept achievement, false positives and lack of knowledge.

Suggestions

In the light of the findings of the present study, following suggestions emerged that can be used by teachers to improve the Mathematics education:

1. Teachers can use the Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics for formative evaluation to assess the misconceptions of the 6th class students about the geometrical concepts.
2. A teacher should focus on students' cognitive level to ensure concept achievement. The major focus of instructions should be on creating links between concrete experiences and abstract concepts.
3. The results of the study show that between achievement and concept achievement, false positives and lack of knowledge may emerge. This information would suggest the teaching practitioners to use a variety of teaching methods and combination of them to bridge this gap between achievement and concept achievement.
4. The findings of the study show that criterion referenced objective type and the two tier tests overestimate the concept achievement of the students, as these do not ask for justification and confidence for their answers. They pay no attention to false positives and lack of knowledge. Therefore, teachers should use three-tier tests to measure the concept achievement of the students.
5. It could also motivate the teachers to use new effective methods of teaching over the traditional ones to achieve students' concept achievement.
6. Text book editors can include activities for experimentation in Mathematics laboratory, more examples, non examples and simple questions related to the concept achievement.

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